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UNDERSTANDING CHANGE IN MATERIALS: Spatial knowledge acquired by visually impaired users through the change in footpath materials.

Dr. Andrew Phillip Payne
Savannah College of Art and Design
apayne@scad.edu

ABSTRACT

Throughout time man has traveled to new places and experienced unfamiliar territories often without fear of what lies ahead. However, in today's world any environment outside of our everyday paths of travel can be challenging and intimidating. This research investigated the role typical footpath materials play in communicating a user's position within an urban environment. While illustrating the importance of detecting changes in materials, it argues that positional information should be available to all users. To examine this phenomenon, this study compared two components: the user, and the material, while also considering their relationship. A theoretical framework was developed to explain this relationship and a methodological design was used to elicit quantitative values. By doing so, the research produced a means of evaluating existing as well as future use of construction materials as a piece of a larger information system.

Keywords: Way-finding, Universal Design, Construction Materials.

GENERAL PREMISE AND RESEARCH CONCEPTS

This paper is an all inclusive look at how each of the elements necessary for site navigation is intertwined. The term way-finding was first used by architect Kevin Lynch in *The Image of the City* (1960), in which he referred to maps, street numbers, directional signs and other elements as "way-finding devices." Although the term is fairly new, the ideas of navigation and orientation are not, and are generally taught under the title of environmental communications (Arthur, 1988).

Throughout this paper words will be used independently and interchangeably with common terms from the fields of design, psychology, sociology and others. In building the vocabulary for this research we begin with Long and Hill (1997) who

Figure 1. Matching Pairs Test Site (Photo by Author, 2007)

define way-finding as "the process of navigating through an environment and traveling to places by relatively direct paths." Where-as way-finding is the process of movement, mobility is "the act or ability to move from one's present position to one's desired position in another part of the environment safely, gracefully, and comfortably" (Long and Hill, 1997). This strategic movement from place-to-place can be classified as both orientation and navigation.

In reviewing much of the literature on way-finding and orientation, no studies were found to combine visually impaired travelers and construction materials when looking at ". . . the physical setting within which way-finding occurs, or the extent to which design features contribute to, or might help resolve, difficulties in way-finding" (Weisman, 1981). Thus, three related questions were formed for the structure of this study. First, it is essential to ask what type of way-finding difficulties are most common; second, which aspects of mobility are the most important for travel; and, thirdly, how are unfamiliar spaces perceived? This research involves an empirical investigation in order to answer these questions, specifically by using a visually impaired sample and implementing changes in footpath materials.

The study was designed to explore spatial knowledge acquired by visually impaired users through the navigation of an urban environment as a means for them to become oriented within a space. This

experience is built upon by direct navigation, or first-person movement through an environment and the encounters with the various design elements of such spaces.

"The difficulty of a way-finding task is affected by two major physical factors: the layout of the setting and the quality of the environmental communication" (Arthur and Passini, 1992). The layout, defined by Romedi Passini, is determined by its spatial context, its form, its organization, and its circulation. Passini also states that environmental communication consists of essential information for way-finding such as the architectural, audible, and graphic expressions. To accommodate all pedestrians, it is important to provide information that can be assimilated using more than one sense. Also, redundancy and consistency increase the likelihood that all users will be able to make informed traveling decisions.

Passini (1992) concluded that people finding their way in complex settings will try to understand how it is organized and will identify things to map mentally. The building blocks used for cognitive mapping are spatial entities, and these spatial entities can only be mapped if they are distinct or unique from their surroundings. The same holds true for decision making. Decision making and execution can be successful only if destinations have an identity distinguishing them from other places. "A place has to be recognized before a decision can be

Figure 2. Way-finding Decision Making (by Author, 2006)

transformed into behavior. Distinctiveness giving places their identity is, thus, a major requirement for way-finding” (Arthur and Passini, 1992).

The materials selected to be compared were originally identified in a study conducted by Jim Gibbons through the Cooperative Extension System at the University of Connecticut. The result of his study was a 1999 technical paper titled *Pavement and Surface Materials*. Gibbons’ paper identifies nine materials used for vehicle and pedestrian thoroughfares and describes the characteristics and procedures for proper construction. Of Gibbons’ original nine materials, three were chosen to be compared and tested in this research: concrete, brick pavers, and stamped concrete. In addition to these three materials, the researcher included four other surface materials: 12-inch slate tiles, 12-inch concrete pavers, manufactured cobblestone and applied non-slip grit over concrete. The added materials were comparable to the original three in size, installation method, availability, and usability. The decision to introduce materials other than those evaluated by Gibbons was based on local observations of types of sidewalks and materials being used in the southeast region of the United States. Certainly, many other sidewalk materials are being used throughout the U.S. and around the globe, therefore, similar research may be required for materials which are more suitable in other locations if these conclusions are to apply to a larger context.

This study contains two primary purposes. The first purpose is to investigate and compare the seven construction materials often used for sidewalks. The second purpose is to determine the best combination or “material adjacency” to produce the greatest level of detection of change in materials among the users. In order to help designers produce the most accessible environment possible, this research will provide a design standard for pathways which can incorporate information cues in the form of changes in materials along the travel path.

The central focus is defined as being the user’s ability to determine their position within a space based on cues from changes in footpath materials. The practical significance of this research is grounded in the underlying premise that way-finding by visually impaired persons within an urban setting can be enhanced through architectural design and planning. The design approach being addressed in this research is that of pedestrian paths and construction materials. The relationship between paths and materials must be determined to provide a clear basis and rationale for future designs.

WAY-FINDING DECISION MAKING

The navigator is charged with matching internal information (experience) and external information (environmental features) as it becomes available. Way-finding decision making involves two essential

	Conc.	Brick Pavers	Stamped Conc.	Slate Tile	12” Conc. Pavers	Cobblestone	Non-slip Grit
Conc.	Same	Conc. & Brick Pavers	Conc. & Stamped Conc.	Conc. & Slate Tile	Conc. & 12” Conc. Pavers	Conc. & Cobblestone	Conc. & Non-slip Grit
Brick Pavers	Same	Same	Brick Pavers & Stamped Conc.	Brick Pavers & Slate Tile	Brick Pavers & 12” Conc. Pavers	Brick Pavers & Cobblestone	Brick Pavers & Non-slip Grit
Stamped Conc.	Same	Same	Same	Stamped Conc. & Slate Tile	Stamped Conc. & 12” Conc. Pavers	Stamped Conc. & Cobblestone	Stamped Conc. & Non-slip Grit
Slate Tile	Same	Same	Same	Same	Slate Tile & 12” Conc. Pavers	Slate Tile & Cobblestone	Slate Tile & Non-slip Grit
12” Conc. Pavers	Same	Same	Same	Same	Same	12” Conc. Pavers & Cobblestone	12” Conc. Pavers & Non-slip Grit
Cobblestone	Same	Same	Same	Same	Same	Same	Cobblestone & Non-slip Grit
Non-slip Grit	Same	Same	Same	Same	Same	Same	Same

Figure 3. Matching Pairs Matrix (by Author, 2006)

components: environmental cognition (recognizing travel paths) and route choice.

Passini (1992) states that not only do design features have to be memorable, but also recognizable by most everybody, in order to function as a cue. “What may be a landmark for one person may not for another” (Arthur and Passini, 1992). It is by designing with redundancy and consistency that spatial communication is most effective. Arthur and Passini (1992) also argued that some distinct features along a path are necessary to serve as anchor points around which people can build their representations. These anchor points or landmarks can also serve to breakdown a long journey into manageable units. Intermediate destination points located within a long and/or complex network of paths can serve as a decision point or cue. While directional changes can make it more difficult to map a path, it is the number of intersections (decision points) that affects the difficulty of decision making. For each decision, people have to obtain and process environmental information.

Unfortunately, each decision point offers the potential for a mistake. “Of course, there is nothing wrong with decision points. After all way-finding is problem solving and decision making. It is the combination of too many decision points and not enough information that gets people lost” (Arthur and Passini, 1992).

RESEARCH METHODS

This section discusses the research methods applied in the study. It presents the reasons for selecting the study site, the subjects, data collection and analysis methods, and the ways of establishing the rigor of the study.

The primary research question is: **What role do changes in footpath materials play in the ability of visually impaired users to locate their position within a space?** The purpose behind this question is to evaluate the pedestrians understanding of their position within a complex urban setting based on the user’s ability to detect changes in footpath materials. Since the primary focus of the research question is on one aspect of the built environment, which is change in construction materials, it is necessary for the purpose of this study to compare multiple combinations of materials.

To answer the research questions, this study required an appropriate context: a locus and a group of people who utilize the space, a device to measure physical properties of the individual surface materials, and a rating scale for detecting change in materials. The research questions also required the selection of a site appropriate for field experiments. In order for a test facility to be capable of providing generalizable data results the site must be active, accessible, local and atypical. Therefore, the research setting chosen for this study was the Governor Morehead School for the Blind (GMS) in Raleigh, North Carolina.

The Governor Morehead School is located on a 40 acre campus that includes several other state departments including the Division of Services for the Blind, Adult Rehabilitation and Training, and the Vision Impairment and Training Program (which operates in conjunction with N.C. Central University). GMS provides pre-school and K-12 education with on-campus housing and support facilities for visually impaired students and those

Figure 4. Matching Pairs Test Routines (by Author, 2007)

with multiple disabilities. Various other services are available daily to visitors of the campus through classes, trainings sessions, meetings, conferences and a mobility aid's store. The GMS site was selected for these field tests for its variety of outdoor spaces, diversity of users and visitors to the campus, and the opportunity to permanently install various materials that can serve as a test area and learning tool for all of the students and guests, now and into the future.

Of those interested in participating, twenty-three visually impaired adults qualified for the study (n=23). All participants were at least eighteen years old and independent and efficient travelers who primarily used the assistance of a long cane. The sample consisted of 14 (61.9%) males and 9 (38.1%) females and had a mean age of 50 years, 3 months (Min = 39; Max = 71). Of these, all were certified as legally blind as determined by the state of North Carolina, and had varying degrees of vision and travel experience.

The data gathering exercise for this study focused solely on a Matching Pairs Test and was conducted at the GMS site. This test consisted of a large enough sample of the population to achieve the desired probability and was able to assess whether or not the changes in materials resulted in a significant response. A major limitation to the sample size was that the focus of this research is so narrow that a very special population was sought. Of the nearly 10 million Americans who are visually impaired, only about 1.2 million are legally blind adults (AFB, 2007). The number is reduced even further when eliminating those with mental or multiple disabilities. Therefore, the availability of qualified subjects for this study was very limited. Aspects of this research could be done with a less specific sample group, however, the primary thesis would have to change.

The materials were locally available and installed by a professional landscaping crew. The test site for the Matching Pairs Test was an existing natural walking path consisting of a four foot wide mulch path leading from a staff and visitor parking lot to the childcare building. The length, width, and

accessibility from within the campus made this site location attractive. Much work was required to construct the sidewalk for the Matching Pairs Test. The installation began with the excavation of the site and preparation and installation of a 4-inch concrete sub-base. The labor and materials were donated from local vendors and contractors, whereas the concrete sub-base was provided at-cost and funded by the researcher. Each finish material was then installed according to the researcher's plan. One crucial design detail was that each joint between adjacent materials had to be non-existent or at least minimally detectible. The contractor exceeded the researcher's expectations and the installation was timely and precise.

This test compared mixed pairs of the sidewalk materials in twenty-three combinations and was conducted in a semi-controlled outdoor environment to limit distractions. The researcher designed the sidewalk to allow for all seven materials to be arranged in such a way that twenty-one unique combinations of adjacent materials were provided, allowing for two duplicate combinations.

Each test was conducted by the researcher who observed one participant at a time. The participant was led to the test area from a neutral meeting place on campus to the starting point of the test route. Each participant was required to bring his/her own long cane for use during the exercise. Since each individual adapts to the unique sense and feel of their own cane, the researcher felt it to be important to not dictate the type of cane used. Instead, the type of cane was noted by the researcher and calculated in the data analysis as a variable (nylon tip, roller tip, or metal tip).

The test procedure involved the researcher positioning the subject at the first intersection of two materials and explaining the process from that point forward. For the determination of textures, the subjects chose the sweep method (a side-to-side motion with the cane tip being in constant contact with the ground surface). In addition to the long cane, subjects also explored sensations underfoot as generated by walking, scuffing, and tapping the foot. This was noted by one subject as: "an effective way

to determine the stability or permanency of a material.” As with the cane type, the researcher did not specify the type of shoes, instead the researcher noted the type worn and calculated in the data analysis as a variable (tennis, casual, or dress).

The researcher allowed a fixed amount of time (30 seconds) to explore the pairs of materials. At the conclusion of each 30 second review period the participant declared a definitive “Yes” or “No” to the two questions by the researcher: 1) As detected by the cane, is there a difference between the two materials? and, 2) As detected underfoot, is there a difference between the two materials? Upon the subject making a determination, the researcher documented the answers and directed the subject to the next intersection and repeated. The researcher also noted (without instigating responses) any descriptive comments made by the subjects. These comments were noted in a final report as possible “keywords” to help describe the surface textures.

MATCHING PAIRS TEST DATA: CANE

A series of binary logistic regression analyses using simultaneous entry were conducted to determine whether cane tip type would predict accuracy in detecting changes in sidewalk materials while en route. Regression results indicate that, for Brick Pavers and Concrete, the overall model approached significance in classifying participants’ responses as

correct or incorrect, $\chi^2(4) = 9.38, p = .05, R^2 = .34$. The model correctly classified 78.3% of the cases as correct or incorrect. Regression results also indicate that, for Concrete and Stamped Concrete, the overall model approached significance in classifying participants’ responses as correct or incorrect, $\chi^2(4) = 8.67, p = .07, R^2 = .31$. The model correctly classified 78.3% of the cases as correct or incorrect. Regression results continued by indicating that, for Slate Tile and Stamped Concrete, the overall model approached significance in classifying participants’ responses as correct or incorrect, $\chi^2(4) = 11.01, p = .03, R^2 = .38$. The model correctly classified 73.9% of the cases as correct or incorrect.

MATCHING PAIRS TEST DATA: UNDERFOOT

Another series of binary logistic regression analyses using simultaneous entry were conducted to determine whether shoe type would predict accuracy in detecting changes in sidewalk materials while en route. Regression results indicate that, for Concrete and Slate Tile, the overall model approached significance in classifying participants’ responses as correct or incorrect, $\chi^2(4) = 12.25, p = .02, R^2 = .41$. The model correctly classified 91.3% of the cases as correct or incorrect. Regression results also indicate that, for Cobblestone and Brick Pavers, the overall model approached significance in classifying participants’ responses as correct or incorrect, $\chi^2(4) = 8.92, p = .06, R^2 = .32$. The model correctly

	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3	Test 4	Test 5	Test 6	Total
Stamped Concrete	32	28	29	31	35	21	176
Brick Pavers	32	30	27	25	34	33	181
Concrete	30	28	30	40	41	32	201
Slate Tile	27	22	40	29	29	39	186
Cobblestone	23	35	34	21	29	41	183
Non-Slip Grit	35	39	33	35	39	30	211
12" Square Conc. Pavers	22	23	39	25	31	32	172

Figure 5. Rank Test Tally (by Author, 2006)

classified 78.3% of the cases as correct or incorrect.

MATCHING PAIRS TEST DATA: RANK TEST

Data sheets were kept for all 23 subjects and tallied upon completion. The responses from the cane tests and underfoot tests were analyzed for the material best detected in the Matching Pairs Test. During each of the subject's evaluations of a pair of materials, if the response was "Yes", each material in that pair received a score of one. At the conclusion of all tests, the material scores were totaled and ranked according to the highest number of positive detections. This simple test was able to determine which individual material (when matched with other materials) was most often detected as being "different". The result was Non-slip Grit with a score of 211 (or 16.1%).

IMPACT ON WAY-FINDING

The success of this research is evident in the positive response and performance of the subjects in detecting the changes in materials. The researcher feels that this method providing way-finding cues along a path can improve decision making and enhance the independent travelers experience in both familiar and unfamiliar environments.

Conclusions from this research can be further utilized to develop design standards as one piece of a more accessible way-finding information system. The improved sidewalk designs will be more inclusive of visually impaired pedestrians, and changes in surface materials will be a method for providing information cues along the journey. It is predicted that with the incorporation of changes in materials at key locations within the footpath network, users will better understand the spatial layout. For example, once the user has learned the overall information system, a detected change in footpath material would indicate one or more of the following: a) change in path direction, b) location of signage, c) building entrance or d) information kiosk, etc.

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